

Grant agreement no. 312788

ORCID AND DATACITE
INTEROPERABILITY NETWORK

<http://odin-project.eu>

D2.2 KICKOFF REPORT

WP2 – Communication

V7_0

Final draft

Abstract: The ODIN kickoff meeting provided an overview of the current persistent identifier discussion, as well as valuable input from key stakeholders to the ODIN project. Eleven presenters from a variety of stakeholder groups provided important perspectives, and the extensive discussion by all meeting participants further elaborated on key points. Based on the key scientific inputs, the following actions were identified:

- i) Encourage discussion and collaboration between communities
- ii) Address specific issues of working with large number of small heterogeneous datasets
- iii) Identify main interoperability use cases and define their business value
- iv) Encourage development of novel tools to track the reuse of data

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1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of the ODIN project is to identify and resolve issues relating to the ‘missing thin layer’ of persistent identifiers needed for a globally connected and interoperable scholarly communication e-infrastructure. The overall aim is to support development and stimulate adoption of interoperable identifiers for researchers, their inputs (cited work, data) and their outputs (publications and data), and to facilitate information flow within and between research communities, leading to greater re-use of data and innovative exploitation of the knowledge created.

ODIN will provide a roadmap which focuses on the integration and scalability of the DataCiteⁱ and ORCIDⁱⁱ persistent identifier initiatives for tackling ODIN's four main challenges concerning research data: *accessibility*, *discovery*, *interoperability*, and *sustainability*. A crucial part of ODIN's strategy is to communicate its project findings and to engage with the relevant communities (see **D2.1 Kick off preparation, Communication plan and Website**). In order to do so, early in the project's progress ODIN organized an international and multidisciplinary kickoff event.

This deliverable is a report from the ODIN kickoff meeting, which highlights the current state of the art and its significance to the ODIN project. In addition to capturing the key outcomes of the meeting, it provides a foundation for the other Work Packages of the project as they analyse issues of interoperability, gaps and the proofs of concept.

2. MEETING SUMMARY

The ODIN kickoff meeting took place October 18th, 2012 at the Kalkscheune in Berlin. The date and the place were chosen to leverage a series of ORCID-sponsored events taking place during that week in Berlinⁱⁱⁱ. The full-day kickoff meeting included 11 presentations and the size and programme of the event provided the right format for many insightful discussions relevant for the ODIN project. The target was an audience of highly-qualified professionals, with a number which would not hamper collective discussion in the generous time allocated to unveil further input following the various presentations. The programme can be found in **Annex A**.

The main goal of the kickoff meeting was to provide scientific input to the ODIN project partners, both through presentations by carefully selected stakeholders from the wider scholarly community, and through discussion of key topics among all participants. The key scientific inputs obtained from the presentations and discussions are summarized in section 4 below.

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Another goal of the kickoff meeting was to introduce the ODIN project to the relevant scientific communities, and to facilitate follow-up conversations in the 24 month duration of the project.

Salvatore Mele and Jan Brase opening the meeting

Ed Pentz presenting the CrossRef experience

3. PRESENTATION SUMMARIES

All presentation slides can be downloaded from the ODIN project website^{iv}.

Paolo Bouquet (OKKAM) - Digital Object Identifiers and Unique Author Identifiers

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Paolo Bouquet is Associate Professor at the Department of Engineering and Information Science of the University of Trento, and President and Co-founder of OKKAM. He coordinated the EU-funded DIGOIDUNA study.

Paolo Bouquet gave a summary of the main findings and recommendations of the DIGOIDUNA study^v. This provided an excellent starting point for the scientific discussions within the ODIN project. He stressed that the main challenge for building a unique identifier infrastructure is not technical, but rather organizational. The digital identifier landscape is still very fragmented, with digital object identifier infrastructure overall more mature than the author identifier infrastructure. In his view it is very important to “cross the boundaries” between the different communities early on and to build a conceptual framework that includes all relevant communities and is scalable. As an example for successful discussion across communities he mentioned the “Den Haag Persistent Identifier – Linked Open Data Manifesto”^{vi}. The DIGOIDUNA study recommends coordinating and supporting better collaboration between the existing initiatives, rather than supporting only one of the existing solutions, doing nothing and waiting for “natural” convergence, or inventing a new unique identifier scheme.

Jan Brase (Datacite) – ODIN: ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network

Jan Brase is the Managing Agent of DataCite and coordinates the DOI registration agency at the German National Library of Science and Technology (TIB). He is the Scientific Coordinator of the ODIN project.

Jan Brase introduced the ODIN project to the meeting participants. He presented the objectives and structure of the project, highlighting the need for input from the relevant communities, and linked the project to the results of the DIGOIDUNA study and to the conclusions of the High-Level Expert Group “Riding the Wave”^{vii}. This offered the participants a framework for the following discussions.

Ed Pentz (CrossRef) – CrossRef: Lessons Learned

Ed Pentz is the Executive Director of CrossRef, the official DOI registration agency for scholarly and professional publications.

Ed Pentz talked about the lessons that CrossRef^{viii} learned from introducing Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for journal articles 12 years ago. The key driver was not the interest in creating a persistent identifier infrastructure at the time, but rather to solve a specific problem, namely reference linking between publishers. The solution to the challenges of many to many linkages was to provide one agreement and one core infrastructure. This focus on a small set of specific problems was important for widespread DOI adoption by the scholarly publisher community. Important side notes were that CrossRef tries to stay away from business models or initiatives that are not strategic for the core CrossRef mission, which is both service and innovation oriented. Ed also highlighted some of the different challenges that DataCite and ORCID are facing: there does not exist the same standardized metadata for datasets as for journal

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articles, data citation is still a new concept compared to journal article citation, and privacy is a particular concern with author identifiers.

Verena Weigert (JISC) – Challenges/Barriers, input from funders

Verena Weigert is a programme manager in the UK Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC) Digital Infrastructure team, coordinating the work on digital identifiers for authors.

Verena Weigert presented the JISC^x perspective towards unique identifiers for objects and authors. The point of view of a funding agency, close to research-performing organisations and universities, is important to frame existing gaps and concrete needs. JISC recommends ORCID as the author identifier that best fits the needs of the United Kingdom researcher community^x, and JISC is also supporting DataCite. The JISC author identifier community and the managing research data community are each very active, but there is little interaction between them. She sees projects like ODIN as potential bridges. JISC tries to focus on the concerns of the researcher community to avoid recommendations biased towards the views of information service providers.

Brigitte Haustein (GESIS) – DOI Registration of Social and Economic Data: First identification, then linking

Brigitte Haustein coordinates the DOI registration service at GESIS, the German Leibniz-Institute for the Social Sciences.

Brigitte Haustein presented the perspective of the GESIS^{xi} data centre for social sciences. Datasets in the social sciences are typically rather small, but have very rich metadata, and often contain time series. GESIS set up a DOI registration service for datasets with DataCite in 2010 to facilitate data citation. Social scientists are conservative, and may need more support with technical infrastructure compared to other disciplines. This is an important point of view from a sector which is in rapid growth in exploring their research data infrastructure needs. She also identified the business need for solving the missing links between datasets and publications and outlined challenges that could be faced in trying to solve this need. GESIS have taken a first identification, then linking approach.

Michael Habib (Elsevier) – Scopus and ORCID

Michael Habib is a product manager at the publisher Elsevier, coordinating work on integrating digital identifiers for objects and authors into the bibliographic database Scopus.

Michael Habib presented the perspective of a large publishing house with a large-scale program in developing database infrastructure underpinning value-added services. He talked about the approach Scopus^{xii} is taking towards unique identifiers for authors and data. Scopus is focusing on research outputs that researchers deem important and

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which are accessible. Data are perceived important, but not easily accessible. One problem is that – in contrast to journal articles – data are very heterogeneous. Scopus is indexing datasets through collaborations with specific data providers, but currently sees little data citation. Scopus is actively integrating ORCIDs and thinks this will help linking journal articles to datasets, therefore overcoming this dichotomy.

Janifer Gatenby (ISNI) – International Standard Name Identifier (ISNI)

Janifer Gatenby is the Program Manager metadata EMEA with the non-profit library service provider OCLC^{xiii} and a member of the ISNI^{xiv} Working Group.

The International Standard Name Identifier (ISNI) is an identifier for public identities of individuals or organizations involved in creating, producing, managing and distributing content. Janifer Gatenby reported that ISNI is focusing on rights management of licensed digital resources, on collaborating in author name disambiguation, and on generating links as assertions of the above. ISNI has a different, and wider, focus than ORCID, and is collaborating with ORCID on how to best integrate the two author identifier services. This is a good example of collaboration between major existing identifier initiatives, as recommended by the DIGOIDUNA study.

Pablo de Castro (UK RepositoryNet+) – Opportunities: Improving Interoperability. Input from Institutional Repositories

Pablo de Castro is Director of Operations at the institutional repositories service provider GrandIR^{xv}, and a consultant with the UK RepositoryNet+.

Pablo de Castro thinks that ORCID and Datacite can enhance the metadata of institutional repositories similar to the already existing integration with CrossRef. Ideally this integration should become part of the default services provided by institutional repositories, with support from repository platform providers. Activities allowing linking to external resources in the long term are important for this community, but do present big challenges in the short term.

Lambert Heller (TIB Hannover) – Opportunities: Improve Interoperability ... from a Library Viewpoint

Lambert Heller is the Head of the Open Science Lab at the German National Library of Science and Technology (TIB).

Lambert Heller stressed that the library world has a wealth information about researchers from many different sources, and that it is a challenge to connect this information. Researchers are not only producing research outputs, but are also linking to them in many ways, e.g. via citations, bookmarking, or discussions in social media. ODIN should think about how to capture these interactions between researchers and datasets, investigating a role for the researcher herself as a provider of information.

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Hideaki Takeda (National Institute of Informatics) – Researcher’s ID in Japan

Hideaki Takeda is the Director of the Research and Development Center for Scientific Information Resources at the Japanese National Institute of Informatics.

Hideaki Takeda reported that Japan has built a national unique identifier infrastructure, including author identifiers, and persistent identifiers for research outputs and grants. The National Institute of Informatics (NII)^{xvi} provides much of this infrastructure. One of the challenges is to connect these author and digital object identifiers to international initiatives. The NII is actively involved in the ORCID initiative. This point of view from Japan is important as it complements the expertise in the European, US and Australian systems, represented by the ODIN project.

Gregg Gordon (SSRN) – Perspective of a US-based Social Science subject repository

Gregg Gordon is the President and CEO of the SSRN, a US-based service for the rapid dissemination of scholarly research in the social sciences and humanities.

Gregg Gordon talked about the experience of the Social Science Research Network (SSRN)^{xvii}. SSRN hosts private and public data, and three quarters of the research data files are Excel. Datasets can have different authors – or a different author order – compared to the associated research papers. He stressed the need to show the benefits of sharing research data so that researchers make the extra effort required for preparing datasets for submission to a repository. Unique identifiers for authors and data play a central role in this.

4. KEY SCIENTIFIC INPUTS

The presentations and subsequent lively discussions at the kickoff meeting touched many topics that the ODIN project is actively working on, and provided unique insights from the wider community that the ODIN consortium otherwise would have missed. These key scientific inputs are listed below.

Are persistent identifiers for data and people a goal in itself, or rather tools to solve specific problems?

In his presentation Ed Pentz made a strong case that, for CrossRef, the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for journal articles was needed to solve a specific problem: namely reference linking between publishers. Solving this specific problem has driven both the adoption of the DOI among publishers and the wider scholarly community, and also CrossRef as an organization. Since the beginning, CrossRef has strived to focus on this core mission. In the same way, Chris Shillum, from Elsevier, also involved in CrossRef from the beginning seconded the usefulness of using DOIs to solve a specific problem as the factor underpinning their wide adoption.

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It was felt that ODIN should explore and discuss how to apply this lesson to persistent identifiers for data and contributors. Specifically, it will be important to consider how the focus on a small number of specific use cases can inform the goal of broader adoption for these persistent identifiers.

Are the different communities sufficiently talking to each other?

A number of communities are involved in the discussions about persistent identifiers for data and contributors. It is not clear that these discussions always cross the boundaries between the communities. For example, is the data citation community sufficiently talking to the author attribution community, or the institutional repositories community to the publisher community, or the semantic web community to the persistent identifier community? Several speakers, including Paolo Bouquet, Verena Weigert and Gregg Gordon, stressed the danger of discussions (and therefore solutions) taking place in silos (regional, national, linguistic or community ones).

The views of information-service providers are, unsurprisingly, well-represented in discussions about persistent identifiers. However, it is important that ODIN also involve the individual researcher community in this discussion and pay attention to their needs. Ultimately, the adoption of persistent identifiers for authors and data may depend on having a single community built on trust among all participants. This is obviously a very big challenge, but in the end could be more important than building the underlying technical infrastructure.

How do we most efficiently promote data citation?

Data citation is commonly seen as an important incentive to make research data openly available. This point was stressed by several speakers, including Jan Brase from DataCite. We should be prepared for data citation becoming part of research assessments. Michael Habib showed how publications, datasets and contributors are linked in Scopus, but that data citations are still relatively rare. We discussed how data citation can be facilitated. One question was how best to conceptualize the relationship among article, data and author: as a triangle, or as linear relationship with the author in the middle?

Lambert Heller demonstrated how researchers are reusing and referring to data and publications, increasingly also by way of social media tools such as Twitter, Mendeley and others. These forms of reuse might better capture the value of datasets to research compared to traditional citations, but provide many unique identifier challenges; e.g. how do we link social media profiles to scholarly author identifiers, and are these reuses always using DataCite DOIs or other persistent, scholarly identifiers rather than non-persistent web links?

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How different are the challenges for small and large datasets?

Gregg Gordon said that many datasets in the social sciences are small, heterogeneous and unstructured data without much documentation (typically in Excel files), and this might also be true for other disciplines. Providing persistent identifiers for data and authors is a different challenge for large numbers of small heterogeneous data without dedicated resources for data curation, compared to datasets created in the large centralized resources (e.g. in high-energy physics and genomics). The discussion showed that even within one discipline the diversity of datasets is striking.

How to accommodate local differences while not losing sight of global commonalities?

Presentations by Verena Weigert, Brigitte Haustein, Pablo de Castro, Lambert Heller, Hideaki Takeda and Gregg Gordon provided unique national perspectives from UK, Germany, Spain, Japan and the US, respectively. Whereas many author and digital object identifier challenges are probably best solved at a global level, there is certainly a need for adjustments to address specific concerns at the European, national and local level.

5. SCIENTIFIC DECISIONS

The scientific input obtained during the kickoff meeting proved valuable in attaching a concrete action to each of the main ODIN challenges. This is summarized in the following table, where the Challenges, Objectives, Activity and Outputs are as taken from the ODIN Description of Work.

Challenge	Objective	Activity	Output	Action
Access	Build shared understanding	Document perceptions, attitudes and barriers	Roadmap of outstanding issues and recommendations	Encourage discussion and collaboration between communities
Discovery	Navigation across data and contributors	Define and implement workflow scenarios for attribution in HSS and HEP	Proofs of concept at two disciplinary extremes	Address specific issues of working with large number of small heterogeneous datasets

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Challenge	Objective	Activity	Output	Action
Interoperability	Demonstrate interoperability	Define mappings between selected identifier systems of DataCite and ORCID members	Mechanisms for integrating multiple identifier systems	Identify main interoperability use cases and define their business value
Sustainability	Stimulate value-added services	Build developer community to exploit interoperable identifiers	Model of interoperable and open identifiers validated at a hackathon	Encourage development of novel tools to track the reuse of data

Each of these concrete actions finds its place in one of the ODIN activities:

Encourage discussion and collaboration between communities. The ODIN roadmap and recommendations will address strategies on how to overcome the fragmentation of the discussion into different stakeholder communities.

Address specific issues of working with large number of small heterogeneous datasets. The HSS proof of concept will specifically look at issues related to working with large numbers of small heterogeneous datasets.

Identify main interoperability use cases and define their business value. The recommendations for interoperability will extend technical specifications, considering specific use cases, including better incentives for data citation.

Encourage development of novel tools to track the reuse of data. The ODIN hackathon will provide opportunities for developers to work on tools to better track and promote data reuse.

ⁱ DataCite, <http://www.datacite.org>

ⁱⁱ ORCID, <http://about.orcid.org>

ⁱⁱⁱ ORCID October 2012 Outreach meeting, <http://about.orcid.org/civicrm/event/info?reset=1&id=6>

^{iv} Kickoff meeting page at ODIN website, <http://odin-project.eu/events/kick-off/>

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^v DIGOIDUNA study, <http://www.digoiduna.eu>

^{vi} Den Haag Manifesto, <http://www.knowledge-exchange.info/Default.aspx?ID=462>

^{vii} Riding the Wave, Report of the High Level Expert Group on Scientific Data, <http://cordis.europa.eu/fp7/ict/e-infrastructure/docs/hlg-sdi-report.pdf>

^{viii} CrossRef, <http://www.crossref.org>

^{ix} JISC, <http://www.jisc.ac.uk>

^x UK specialists welcome launch of ORCID as tool to identify researchers, <http://www.jisc.ac.uk/news/stories/2013/01/UK%20specialists%20welcome%20launch%20of%20ORCID%20as%20tool%20to%20identify%20researchers.aspx>

^{xi} GESIS, <http://www.gesis.org>

^{xii} Scopus, <http://www.scopus.com>

^{xiii} OCLC, <http://www.oclc.org>

^{xiv} ISNI, <http://www.isni.org>

^{xv} GrandIR, <http://www.grandir.com/en/>

^{xvi} National Institute of Informatics, <http://www.nii.ac.jp/en/>

^{xvii} SSRN, <http://www.ssrn.com>

ANNEX A - KICKOFF MEETING DETAILS

Programme

08:30-09:00 Registration

9:00 - 10:30 Introduction/Vision

Welcome, Salvatore Mele (CERN)

The DIGOIDUNA study: main conclusions and moving forward, Paolo Bouquet (OKKAM)

The ODIN vision: introduction to the project, Jan Brase (DataCite)

Lessons learned by CrossRef, Ed Pentz (CrossRef)

10:30 - 11:00 Coffee Break

11:00 - 12:30 Challenges/Barriers, Moderation: Salvatore Mele (CERN)

Input from funders, Verena Weigert (JISC)

Input from data centers, Brigitte Hausstein (GESIS)

Input from citation databases, Michael Habib (Scopus/Elsevier)

12:30 - 13:30 Lunch Break

13:30 - 15:00 Opportunities: Improve Interoperability, Moderation: Laure Haak (ORCID EU)

Input from ISNI/VIAF (Janifer Gatenby)

Input from institutional repositories, Pablo de Castro (GrandIR)

Input from libraries, Lambert Heller (TiB Hannover)

15:00 - 15:30 Coffee Break

15:30 - 16:30 Opportunities: We are not Alone, Moderation: Jude England (British Library)

Input from Japan, Hideaki Takeda (National Institute of Informatics, Japan)

Input from US, Gregg Gordon (SSRN)

16:30 - 17:00 Wrap-up, Conclusions, "Take home message" for ODIN, Moderation: Jan Brase (DataCite)

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Mrs. DAGIENE, Eleonora	The Association of Lithuanian Serials	Vilnius	LITHUANIA
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